

A User-Friendly Platform for Bridging the Gap between Carbon Credit Demand and Supply

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Introduction

Demand and supply platforms are digital tools that facilitate the connection between those who need a product or service (demand) and those who provide it (supply). These tools optimize the exchange process by enabling quick and direct access to the necessary resources, reducing geographical barriers, and improving market efficiency. In contexts such as environmental resources and carbon credits, online platforms play a crucial role by allowing businesses, governments, and individuals to buy and sell carbon credits with transparency, traceability, and ease of use.

In the case of sustainable forest management, a dedicated platform connects forest owners and managers who generate carbon credit through sustainable practices with companies and individuals interested in purchasing these credits to offset their carbon emissions. The platform thus facilitates not only the buying and selling of carbon credits but also encourages the promotion of more sustainable forest management practices and the spread of internationally recognized certifications, contributing to global efforts to mitigate climate change.

The growing demand for carbon credit presents an opportunity for forest owners and managers to monetize their sustainable forest management efforts, while contributing to the global fight against climate change. However, a key barrier to accessing these markets has been the complexity and lack of transparent systems for registering and trading carbon credits. To address this, a user-friendly, digital platform has been developed to facilitate the exchange of Sustainability Credits for forests managed in a sustainable way.

A concrete example of this approach is the GO CO₂ Marche initiative. This Operational Group aims to enhance CO₂ sequestration in managed forests by considering not only tree biomass but also forest soils (litter and organic horizons). The project, funded under the Rural Development Programme (PSR Marche 2014-2020), is structured in two phases: an initial six-month Setting-Up phase, followed by a two-year development phase. GO CO₂ Marche promotes Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) through the creation of a dedicated SFM Manual, adjustments to existing management plans, and third-party voluntary certification.

Moreover, the project focuses on scientific methodologies to measure and assess key forest indicators, including aboveground biomass, litter, and soil properties. Experimental forestry sites will be used to compare silvicultural techniques that maximize ecosystem services. Additionally, the initiative includes training programs for local forest workers and partners, ensuring skill development in best management practices and effective communication.

As part of the project, a voluntary sustainability credit exchange platform was developed, facilitating the recognition of carbon storage as an economic asset within the Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES) framework. monetize their carbon sequestration efforts while promoting broader participation in carbon markets.

The platform connects two main categories of users:

Forest Owners/Managers: Those who own or manage forests that generate carbon credit through additional sustainability practices, such as those involved in projects with additionality certification.

Companies/Citizens: Entities or individuals who wish to offset their emissions by purchasing carbon credits from sustainable forest projects.

How the Platform Works

The platform is designed to be as simple and accessible as possible for both forest owners and potential buyers.

Figure 1 - Platform CO2 Marche available at <https://www.co2marche.it/cms/it>

For Forest Owners/Managers

Forest owners or managers who wish to sell carbon credits generated from their forests can register their properties through the platform. The registration process requires the following information:

Personal Information

- Name
- Organization
- Surname
- VAT Number

- Tax Code
- Email Address
- Phone Number
- Forest Details

Location of the Forest

- Address, Province, Municipality, and Country
- Land Registry Information (for example, "Sheet No. 200, Plot No. 13, 15, 20.")
- A Land Registry Extract can be uploaded for further validation.
- Forest Size
- Total hectares of the forest involved in the carbon credit generation.
- Certification

Type of Certification

- Specify the forest's certification status (e.g., GFS or other recognized standards).
- Upload the relevant Certification Document.

Carbon Sequestration Data

- Additional Carbon Sequestration

Estimate the total tonnes of additional carbon generated through sustainable forest management.

- Sustainability Credits for Sale

Indicate how many Sustainability Credits are available for sale based on carbon sequestration.

- Price per Ton of Carbon

Set a price in €/ton of carbon for the sale offer.

Once the forest details and carbon data are registered, the platform allows forest owners to list their Sustainability Credits for Sale. The managers of the platform can validate the information provided and find some companies/citizens that would like to buy the credits. This system ensures that only forests with valid certifications and verified sequestration data are eligible to generate credits, ensuring the credibility of the carbon market.

For Companies / Citizens

Buyers of carbon credit, such as companies and individuals seeking to offset their emissions, can browse available credits from certified forests. They can view the details of the forest certification, the number of credits for sale, and the price per tonne of carbon. By purchasing these credits, buyers contribute to promoting sustainable forest management and reducing their carbon footprint.

Additional Features of the Platform

The platform goes beyond simply facilitating the buying and selling of carbon credits. It serves as a comprehensive tool for Incentivizing Best Practices. In fact, the platform helps incentivize forest managers to adopt Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) practices and obtain third-party certifications.

By making carbon credits a tangible asset, forest managers are encouraged to enhance forest health and carbon sequestration.

Lesson Learned

From the point of view of the ecosystem services generated, if these values were confirmed for all the certified areas of the project (Bosco di Marca Group), the active management actions would lead to the absorption of several thousand

tonnes of CO₂, contributing in parallel to the creation of new business opportunities for forest managers. In fact, considering the additional actions, such as the conversion of coppice to tall trees, that could be carried out in beech forests and areas with mixed deciduous trees (which account for approximately 2/3 of the certified surface area), it would be possible to store up to a maximum of approximately 24,000 tonnes of CO₂ more each year (i.e., 24,000 sustainability credits). This does not take into account the increase in other co-benefits derived from Sustainable Forest Management, such as enhanced biodiversity, improved water resource management, reduced erosion phenomena, and a positive image linked to tourism related to nature enjoyment.

Conclusion

This platform provides a simple yet powerful tool to connect sustainable forest managers with carbon credit buyers, facilitating the transition to a low-carbon economy. It also supports the broader goals of climate change mitigation and biodiversity conservation by incentivizing responsible forest management practices and promoting the global trade of carbon credits.

Further information

<https://www.co2marche.it/>

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